

ECP-2005-EDU-038208

JEM-Joining Educational Mathematics

D 2.3.2 – Portal Assessment Report, August 2007

Deliverable number	<i>D 2.3.2</i>
Dissemination level	<i>Public</i>
Delivery date	<i>22 August, 2007</i>
Status	<i>Final</i>
Author(s)	<i>Matti Pauna</i>

eContentplus

This project is funded under the *eContentplus* programme¹,
a multiannual Community programme to make digital content in Europe more accessible, usable and
exploitable.

¹ OJ L 79, 24.3.2005, p. 1.

D 2.3.2 Portal Assessment Report, August 2007

This report evaluates and assesses the activity of the thematic network portal established in October 2006 at the url <http://www.jem-thematic.net> on the period January - July 2007. The purpose of this deliverable is to discuss the architecture of the portal and its efficacy in disseminating and promoting the goals of the JEM network. This deliverable is public and allows comments and feedback in the effort to improve the service offered by the JEM web site.

1 Portal Architecture

The JEM portal is the main entry point to all information and activities of the network. In the front page newest announcements and events are highlighted. Visitors can find more detailed information about the network, its purpose and partners. Also articles and presentations published by the network members can be found.

JEM - Joining Educational Mathematics
eContentPlus Thematic Network

[Login](#) [Contact](#) [Search](#)

JEM

- ※ Home
- ※ Network Rules
- ※ About us
- ※ Publications
- ※ Related Projects
- ※ FAQs
- ※ News

The goal of the JEM thematic network is to pool together the required expertise and to contribute to the coordination of content enrichment activities in the area of mathematics, to the maintenance of agreed standards and to the delivery of powerful synoptic high-quality user information and support pages, invoked in e-learning platforms operated by the partners.

NEW AND EMERGING TECHNOLOGIES IN MATH EDUCATION

Submitted by mika.seppala on Wed, 07/04/2007 - 15:03 [JEM Workshop](#)

Start: 08/17/2007 - 10:00
 End: 08/18/2007 - 16:00
 Timezone: Etc/GMT+3

Porthania Building, Lecture Hall IV
Vliopistonkatu 3
University of Helsinki
August 17-18, 2007
 SLurl: EdTech(68,62,39)

[Login](#) or [register](#) to post comments
 [Read more](#) 612 reads
 [Calendar](#)
[report as spam](#)

JEM WORKSHOP ON IDENTIFYING AND SUPPORTING (SCIENTIFIC) COMMUNITIES IN EDUCATION AND RESEARCH

Submitted by crussler on Mon, 07/02/2007 - 13:59 [JEM Workshop](#)

Start: 08/30/2007 - 09:00
 End: 08/30/2007 - 17:00
 Timezone: Etc/GMT+2

UPCOMING EVENTS

- New and Emerging Technologies in Math Education (23 hours) (Event)
- JEM Workshop on identifying and supporting (scientific) communities in education and research (14 days) (Event)
- Establishment of review process and related criteria for assessment (77 days) (Deliverable item)
- 3rd Periodic Report (169 days) (Deliverable item)
- Portal Assessment Report (169 days) (Deliverable item)
- JEM directory of e-authors (169 days) (Deliverable item)

[more](#)

ONLINE NOW

There are currently *0 users* and *2 guests* online.

EVENTS

« August 2007 »

Sun	Mon	Tue	Wed	Thu	Fri	Sat
			1	2	3	4
5	6	7	8	9	10	11
12	13	14	15	16	17	18
19	20	21	22	23	24	25
26	27	28	29	30	31	

Members of the network can create accounts and once approved they can access contents that is available only for the JEM network. These include joint publishing areas (wikis) for various interest groups inside the community, e.g. Developers' and Authors' wikis. Also members can post articles and deliverables through the portal.

2 Revision of the portal

A major reimplementation of the portal took place in April – May 2007. A new platform technology, namely Drupal (<http://drupal.org>) was chosen. The platform is more advanced than the previous one and allows extensibility through many modules. For example, a wiki area is easy to embed in the portal with a specific drupal module.

The previous content and registered users were imported to the new portal as such. The layout of the portal was changed a little to be more clear and updated. Major benefit of the new platform is that now it includes all contents of the project in the same place. Especially users do not have to have different accounts for the public portal and network restricted areas.

3 Statistics

These statistics of the use of the JEM portal were produced with the Awstats statistics reporting system.

Month	Unique visitors	Number of visits	Pages	Hits	Bandwidth
Jan 2007	422	832	12325	33722	269.25 MB
Feb 2007	549	1553	9561	20591	156.15 MB
Mar 2007	546	1648	10198	23812	221.37 MB
Apr 2007	475	1519	5017	9191	85.40 MB
May 2007	1632	3337	13121	22746	193.77 MB
Jun 2007	2029	3617	19627	35607	315.81 MB
Jul 2007	1820	3661	27863	55847	675.54 MB
Aug 2007	1064	2190	11472	25085	291.35 MB
Sep 2007	0	0	0	0	0
Oct 2007	0	0	0	0	0
Nov 2007	0	0	0	0	0
Dec 2007	0	0	0	0	0
Total	8537	18357	109184	226601	2.16 GB

D 2.3.2 Portal Assessment Report, August 2007

The trend of the number of monthly visitors has increased clearly. Lot of activities in the web site happened in May and June because of the release of the new portal and the JEM workshop organized in June. A summary of users by country on the period January-August is presented below:

Countries (Top 25) - Full list					
Countries		Pages	Hits	Bandwidth	
United States	us	6181	12021	160.27 MB	
Netherlands	nl	867	1153	11.47 MB	
Sweden	se	436	2072	15.81 MB	
Great Britain	gb	434	600	4.65 MB	
European country	eu	426	1217	19.04 MB	
Germany	de	414	1071	11.20 MB	
China	cn	397	397	6.74 MB	
Finland	fi	337	2160	13.45 MB	
Australia	au	275	583	7.33 MB	
Taiwan	tw	258	281	3.27 MB	
Italy	it	209	255	2.17 MB	
Denmark	dk	127	166	1.11 MB	
Unknown	ip	123	530	4.21 MB	
South Korea	kr	113	113	846.65 KB	
Portugal	pt	97	118	330.91 KB	
Russian Federation	ru	93	137	1.41 MB	
South Africa	za	77	125	1.15 MB	
Canada	ca	73	230	6.71 MB	
Greece	gr	61	163	1.30 MB	
Belgium	be	46	89	833.52 KB	
Hong Kong	hk	45	157	3.72 MB	
Switzerland	ch	44	174	2.30 MB	
Norway	no	43	153	1.37 MB	
France	fr	38	99	1.05 MB	
Spain	es	33	96	1.18 MB	
Others		225	925	8.48 MB	

The visit duration graph shows that many visitors used the portal for longer than 15 minutes.

Visits duration		
Number of visits: 2190 - Average: 578 s	Number of visits	Percent
0s-30s	1487	67.8 %
30s-2mn	126	5.7 %
2mn-5mn	70	3.1 %
5mn-15mn	87	3.9 %
15mn-30mn	95	4.3 %
30mn-1h	134	6.1 %
1h+	188	8.5 %
Unknown	3	0.1 %

D 2.3.2 Portal Assessment Report, August 2007

Number of overall visits in the period September 2006 – August 2007 gathered from the previous sites and the new combined site at the moment is **20086**. The following table shows number of unique visitors, number of visits, downloaded pages, hits and bandwidth of the web site in this year up to August 21.

Summary					
Reported period	Year 2007				
First visit	01 Jan 2007 - 00:48				
Last visit	22 Aug 2007 - 00:02				
	Unique visitors	Number of visits	Pages	Hits	Bandwidth
Traffic viewed *	<= 8981 Exact value not available in 'Year' view	19361 (2.15 visits/visitor)	118185 (6.1 Pages/Visit)	244382 (12.62 Hits/Visit)	2.31 GB (125.24 KB/Visit)
Traffic not viewed *			405492	418646	9.50 GB

* Not viewed traffic includes traffic generated by robots, worms, or replies with special HTTP status codes.

4 Concluding Remarks

The JEM portal has been successfully revised to make it easier to use for the community. Most importantly, the problem of multiple sites and accounts has been solved. Much content, like blog items, presentations in conferences and articles have been published by the network members. The statistics clearly show an increasing interest to the web site and therefore to the JEM community.